

DRAWABILITY OF CFRP/HSS HYBRID COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the formability of the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite material is evaluated during square cup deep drawing by considering the process parameters.

The experimental results show a decrease in the forming depth with an increase in the blank holder force and punch velocity. The best drawing results are obtained when the blank holder force is 40 kN, and the punch velocity is 8 mm/s. In addition, it is evident that the changes in the blank holder force have the most influence on the forming depth.

The changes in the carbon fibre orientation in each region are observed. In the case of the bend-and-straighten region, there is no change in the carbon fibre orientation because there is only simple bending of the material. However, in the case of the deep draw region, there is an abrupt change in the carbon fibre orientation according to the drawing process.

Different changes in thicknesses of the materials are observed according to the region. In the case of the CR340LA, the thickness decreases at the die and punch radii.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, the weight reduction of automobiles has become a hot topic as environmental regulations and gas mileage regulations have been reinforced. On the other hand, the weight of automobiles is continuing to increase because of their advanced performance and increasing number of devices added for convenience. Thus, there are many studies on weight reduction using aluminium alloy, magnesium alloy, titanium alloy, and high strength steel (HSS) in place of steel materials. In addition, advanced high strength steel (AHSS) and composite materials are used to reduce weight. One of these composite materials is carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP), which has a higher strength-to-weight ratio and rigidity than steel materials while being lighter than aluminium. Therefore, CFRP must be studied to reduce the weight of automobiles.

There are also many ongoing studies on the use of pre-impregnated carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP prepreg) [2, 3, 4]. Prepreg is intermediate material of FRP, wherein resin, which is a matrix, is pre-impregnated into fibres.

In addition to the above, studies using carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) are also in progress. Isogawa et al. used a hemispherical punch in their research [5], while Behrens et al. used deep drawing [6]. On the other hand, Hineno et al. studied the changes in the orientation of the fibre by press forming a rectangular cup using two steps [7].

CR340LA is a material used in automobile pillars, which play a very important role in the safety and protection of the passengers by absorbing the shock during a car crash. However, CRFP has mechanical properties that vary according to the fibre orientation and forming processes. Because of its low elongation and fracture toughness, there are many limitations to its application in automobile parts. Thus, many studies are being performed to overcome such problems using hybrid CFRP-metal composite materials. However, there is insufficient.

In the deep drawing of a cylindrical cup, the changes in the fibre orientation with regard to the side wall region of the drawn part are all the same. However, in the bending forming process, a straight flange, stretch flange, shrink flange, and combination jogged flange and reverse flange exist. Various bent shapes are involved in the fabrication of an automobile's pillar, and additional research on such fabrication through square cup deep drawing would be needed.

During the square cup deep drawing of the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite material in this study, the formability was evaluated by considering the process parameters. In addition, the hybrid CFRP-steel composite material was investigated through macroscopic and microscopic observations of the forming depth and fibre orientation.

2 EXPERIMENT PROCEDURE

Experimental method and equipment for square cup deep drawing.

Fig.3 schematic diagram for square cup deep drawing process.

In this experiment, CR340LA and the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite were used for the square cup deep drawing process. Tables 1 and 2 list the details of the materials used. The size of the blank was 90 mm (a) × 80 mm (b). As previously explained, the size of the blank was decided by considering the depth of the square cup to be formed and the shape of the pre-made die as much as possible. The thickness of the CR340LA was 0.7 mm. In case of CFRP, seven 0.27-mm-thick sheets were laminated for a total thickness of 1.89 mm. The thickness of the blank (t_0) was 2.59 mm. Table 3 and Figure 3 give the die dimensions and schematic diagram, respectively, of the die used in the experiment. Table 4 lists the thicknesses and number of layers of the materials. In addition, Table 5 lists the symbols used in the research, along with their definitions and brief descriptions.

The blank holder force and punch velocity were varied during the test. The die and blank holder were heated using cartridge heaters, and the temperatures were controlled separately.

In this experiment, the blank was first placed on the die, after which the blank holder was used to clutch the material. Then, the drawing was performed by applying a constant punch speed. Unlike circular cup deep drawing, the drawn part had a rectangular cup shape. Because of the shape of the die, the drawn part was affected by the die shoulder radius ($R_{d,s}$), die corner radius ($R_{d,c}$), punch bottom radius ($R_{p,b}$), and punch corner radius ($R_{p,c}$).

Measurement of temperature change in material.

During each of the square cup deep drawing processes using the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite, the die and blank holder had to be heated to at least a certain temperature in order to satisfy the curing condition of the semi-cured CFRP. To allow this to take place, cartridge heaters ($\varnothing 16 \text{ mm} \times 40 \text{ mm}$, 400 w) and thermocouples ($\varnothing 1.5 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$, K type) were connected to a temperature controller (OKE-2005CA, Sewon OKE) and installed on the die and blank holder.

The regions considered to be important for measuring the heat transferred to the blank were marked. These included the flange region where it was pressed by the blank holder, the side wall region where the blank was formed by the punch, and the bottom region where the punch came into contact. To obtain accurate measurements, a strainmeter (TC-31K, Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo), which is a portable measuring device, was also used to double-check the temperature of the experiment equipment. The general thermocouple broke as a result of the abrupt inflow of the material during the square cup deep drawing process. Therefore, it was impossible to measure the temperature, and a thermocouple wire (TT-K-36, $\varnothing 0.127 \text{ mm}$, K type, OMEGA) was used instead. Although an adhesive product is commonly used to attach a thermocouple inside a blank, the semi-cured state of the CFRP prepreg was

sufficient to provide the needed adhesiveness.
Measurement of thinning rate.

During the square cup deep drawing of the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite, the changes in the thickness of the material were measured according to the region. The final drawn sample was cut into quarters to allow the thickness to be measured. The cut surface was ground because of the possibility of producing fibre fractures or burrs from this cutting. The thinning rate was obtained using the equation shown below.

(1)(where γ : thinning rate [%], t_0 : initial blank thickness [mm], t : blank thickness after the square cup deep drawing [mm])

3 EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiment results

Temperature changes in material during square cup deep drawing. The temperature was measured according to the region of the blank for each of the deep drawing processes using the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite. The results are presented in Figure 4 as the change in temperature over time.

Fig.4 Temperature distribution of CR340/CFRP hybrid composite according to forming process time.

The important regions selected included the blank installation region (Figure 4(a)), region where the blank holder clutched the blank (Figure 4(b)), and region where the punch formed the material at a constant rate (Figure 4(c)), for a total of three regions. These three regions are schematically illustrated. As seen in Figure 4(a), although there were changes in the temperature in the region where the blank was placed on the die, there were no abrupt changes detected. Nevertheless, this region is considered

to be an important region because the heat is transferred at this location to allow a smooth flow of the semi-cured epoxy.

Figure 4(b) shows the region where the blank holder clutched the blank. Here, an abrupt change in temperature can be observed in the flange region belonging to the blank because of the constant pressure and heat. The change in temperature present in this region takes place over a very short period of time. The time required to reach the target temperature past the blank installation region is approximately 10 s.

As shown in Figure 4, there is no area of contact with the die or blank holder in the case of the region of contact between the blank and punch. Thus, a very gradual increase of temperature can be observed from the blank installation. However, as the punch begins forming at a constant velocity, a rapid increase in temperature can be observed. The major factor in this may be the punch, which has transferred heat from the blank holder, whereas a minor factor could be the heat transfer due to the side wall region of the die being in contact with the blank because of forming. However, as shown in Figure 4, it was observed that the initially set temperature was not reached, and that even if it was reached, a significantly long period of time would be required. Because of the characteristics of the punch shape, a cartridge heater could not be used. This was because the alignment of the axis was a priority in the equipment fabrication to eliminate any defects from misalignment of the axis when fixing the square punch onto the equipment. However, another defect occurred due to the characteristics of the punch shape, which will be discussed later.

(a) $v_p = 8 \text{ mm/s}$

(b) $v_p = 22 \text{ mm/s}$

Fig.5 Relationship between punch load (kN) and forming depth (δ) according to blank holding force (B_f) and punch velocity (V_p) in square cup deep drawing of

CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composites.

Figure 5 shows the results according to the blank holder force and punch velocity during the square cup deep drawing of the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite material. The forming depths were 17.468, 12.890, and 12.612 mm, as shown in Figure 5(a); 15.580, 15.843, and 13.281 mm, as shown in Figure 5(b); and 15.746, 15.799, and 13.808 mm, as shown in Figure 5(c). It can be observed that the formability improved compared to the deep drawing process using only the CR340LA material. The reason for this improvement can be explained as follows. The tensile force required for the deformation of the flange region is transferred to the drawn side wall region by the punch. Here, the side wall region is deeply involved in the fracture, and the force that can be transferred by the side wall region becomes the limiting drawing load. Therefore, once a certain amount of the drawing load reaches the side wall region, a fracture occurs in the blank. Here, the effect of the hybrid composite material has much application. As the drawing load is dispersed to the two materials, the drawing load transferred to the CR340LA relatively decreases.

This result can particularly be observed when the blank holder force is small, and the punch velocity is relatively slow. In other words, such results are present when the forming speed is slow. On the other hand, in the case of experimenting with the hybrid composite material (Figure 5), it can be observed that the fracture occurs after the load abruptly increases. It seems that the fracture occurs as the load that had been borne by the carbon fibres is transferred to the CR340LA after the carbon fibres are fractured from withstanding the load.

Moreover, when forming over the forming limit, it was observed that the fracture occurred in the punch radius region, wherein a fracture was present in both the CR340LA and carbon fibres.

Fig.6 Top view of square cup and forming depth(δ) after square cup deep drawing according to $v = 8$

mm/s: (a) = 40kN, $\delta = 17.47$ mm; (b) = 40kN, (c) = 90kN, $\delta = 12.61$ mm; (d) = 90kN, $\delta = 13.11$ mm

Figures 6 show samples where the blank holder force was varied while maintaining a constant punch velocity. As presented, it can be seen that most of the inflow to the blank occurs with the smallest blank holder force. In this test, it was observed that the formability abruptly decreased when a blank holder force above a certain strength was applied. A decrease in the formability was also observed when the punch velocity was increased, but it was not as large as that due to the effect from the blank holder force.

Results of thinning rate measurements. The thinning rate measurements obtained from measuring the change in thickness of each region during deep drawing using the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite are explained below. Six points were selected for measurement. The measurement points were the regions affected by the die and punch radii during the square cup deep drawing, the region affected by the holding force, the region affected by the tolerance and clearance, the region affected by the punch bottom, and the region affected by the characteristics of the punch.

(a) $B_f = 40kN$

(b) $B_f = 90kN$

Fig.7 Thinning rate at each position in comparison with blank holding force (B_f) according to punch velocity (v_p) in sample.

Figure 7 . Based on these results, it can be said that even though the forming depth of the drawn part is

affected by the blank holder force, the amount of load applied by the punch is almost the same. This is because the force that can be transferred by the side wall region is the limiting drawing load. In addition, it seems that since this is similar to the maximum forming force, the thinning rates at these positions are similar because similar forces are applied. However, even though the thickness decreases at position 2, there are cases where the thickness increases as a result of the deep drawing, characteristics of the fibre, and flow of the epoxy.

Change in fibre orientation due to square cup deep drawing. During square cup deep drawing using the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid material, the carbon fibre orientation changes in several ways. Because of the characteristics of square cup deep drawing, a bend-and-straighten region exists where the material simply enters, along with a deep draw region where the material undergoes compressive deformation. In the boundary region between these regions, shearing deformation occurs as the bend-and-straighten region pulls the material from the deep draw region due to the inflow of the material.

Fig.8 The various carbon fiber orientations according to each locations after the square cup deep drawing.

This causes various fibre orientations, as shown in Figure 8. It shows the region where the fibre orientation abruptly changes in the drawn part due to the square cup deep drawing. As presented in case #1 in Figure 8, the material is pulled into the bend-and-straighten region as it flows in. Thus, a plain weave with a petal shape arrangement is present overall. In case #2 in Figure 8, the arrangement

is concentrated to one side because of the difference in the material inflow amounts between the bend-and-straighten region and deep draw region. In case #3 in Figure 8, not much difference is observed because of the simple inflow. However, when taking a closer look and comparing it to the image of the fibre in #4 in Figure 8, it can be observed that there is a greater interval distance in the direction of the epoxy flow. Case #5 in Figure 8 shows the punch radius region, where it can be observed that the fibre undergoes a change in orientation of greater than 90°. This is because the amount of material that can flow from the bend-and-straighten region and deep draw region by simple flow is relatively too small. Last, in case #6 of Figure 8, the die corner radius, there are relatively numerous changes in the positions of the material, even if the area where the material can flow is small. Therefore, the plain weave carbon fibres have a diamond shape. The details of the changes in the fibre orientation will be discussed later.

Fig.9 Microstructures of CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composites at die shoulder and punch bottom radii according to blank holding force at $v = 8\text{mm/s}$.

Microscopic observation by position of drawn part. Figure 9 shows the microstructures at every position of the drawn part that was formed using the square cup deep drawing. Although a slight void

and delamination are observed due to simple compressive moulding in #1 in Figure 9 (flange region), it can be seen that the defects are very small. The region with the least change in thickness is case #2 in Figure 14 (die shoulder radius region). Here, most of the defects are due to the small amount of pressure received. In case #3 in Figure 9 (side wall region), a small number of defects was observed since the thickness decreased in an even manner. In case #4 in Figure 9 (punch bottom radius), an excessive change in the formation of the fibres due to the excessive thickness reduction can be observed compared to the results of #3 in Figure 9. In case #5 in Figure 9 (punch bottom region), few defects are observed since it also has a simple compression similar to #1 in Figure 9 (flange region). Most of the voids and delamination defects are present in #6 in Figure 9, where the punch shape is unique, because no pressure is received. Similar to #2 in Figure 9, there are many voids since there is no opportunity for the defects to decrease because of the inflow of the flange region. Moreover, the defects are considerably larger than those of other regions.

Discussion

Epoxy pooling effect. In this study, several types of defects were observed during the square cup deep drawing of the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite. The mechanism behind the occurrence of such defects and changes in the fibre orientation from the process are explained below.

As shown in Figure 1, the epoxy pooling effect (call the epoxy ring) was present during the square cup deep drawing. This is illustrated in a schematic diagram explaining the process. As shown in the laminated sequence, the CR340LA was in contact with the die, after which seven sheets of CFRP were laminated. The process schematic diagram is shown on the upper left side, illustrating four stages that are considered to be important.

In CR340LA, which is a sheet metal material, there was barely any change from the blank holder force in the thickness direction.

In this stage, the growth of both the flange epoxy ring and punch epoxy ring is completed. Although the load is concentrated in the punch bottom radius region during the actual forming stage, the punch bottom region also received pressure. Thus, the epoxy ring is also observed because of the previously noted uniqueness of the punch shape. This epoxy ring is referred to as the "punch bottom epoxy ring." In addition, delamination is observed, which is the same defect as observed in #2. In the case of the punch bottom epoxy ring, it seems that this defect can easily be removed by changing the shape of the punch. It is considered that the punch shape must be changed to properly transfer the load from the punch bottom region to the CFRP.

The drawn parts require secondary trimming to eliminate the epoxy ring caused by the outflow of the epoxy resin, or the excess epoxy resin must be absorbed using a bleeder before the epoxy resin is cured.

As previously noted, the changes in orientation at the six main positions are illustrated in Figure 8. If position #5 is regarded as the origin in a coordinate plane that is used to determine the quadrants, the deep draw region would be the first quadrant, and the bend-and-straighten region would belong to the second and fourth quadrants. The punch bottom region would belong to the third quadrant. In the case of the third quadrant, there would simply be a position change in the z axis due to the inflow of the epoxy. In the case of the second and fourth quadrants, the side wall region is formed as the epoxy fills in. In the case of the third quadrant, the die or punch corner radius must be formed with the inflow of the epoxy. However, the shape shown in Figure 8 is formed as a result of the difference in the area that allows the epoxy to flow in.

Various changes in the fibre orientation occurred at each position by the square cup deep drawing. These led to various mechanical properties for the material Defects in square cup deep drawing

When comparing the actual elongation, the official elongation of CR340LA is 27%, whereas that of the CFRP is only 1.5%. Thus, in the actual square cup deep drawing, it can be considered that the carbon fibre just fills in with barely any elongation. However, in the case of CR340LA, when it receives a load, both the inflow of the material and an elongation due to the load occur. Here, the flange region is compressed as the blank enters because the amount that enters the deep draw region is small. At this point, wrinkling occurs because of the absence of the CFRP that had been supporting the CR340LA. In addition, the loosening of the carbon fibres of the flange region was observed because the blank holder tightly held onto the material. The carbon fibres became loose because there was no

part that could support or hold onto the last carbon fibre because of the characteristics of the plain weave carbon fibre. However, from the point of view of the initial blank, the blank enters the space in the die because of the punch, while the carbon fibres on the edge receive a load from the blank holder. Thus, the blank cannot be supported or held, and so the carbon fibres of the blank are caused to fall toward the cavity of the die by the punch. In addition, an epoxy ring can be observed, as previously explained. It can be observed that the punch epoxy ring has grown the most. Aside from the punch epoxy ring, there is also a small number of flange epoxy rings and punch bottom epoxy rings. Voids and delamination were observed at the die shoulder radius. They occurred for the same reason as the epoxy pooling effect described above. It is thought that these problems could be solved by using dummy sheets or a sandwich panel.

4 Conclusion

In this study, the effects of the process parameters on the formability and behaviour of the CR340LA/CFRP hybrid composite material were investigated during square cup deep drawing. The following conclusions were reached in this square cup deep drawing.

1. During the square cup deep drawing of the CR340LA, it was observed that the forming depth decreased as the blank holder force and punch velocity increased. It was evident that the changes in the blank holder force had the most influence on the forming depth. A slight improvement in the formability was also noticed during deep drawing using the CR340LA/CFRP.
2. During the square cup deep drawing of the CR340LA/CFRP, a decrease in the forming depth was observed when the blank holder force and punch velocity increased. The best drawing results were obtained when the blank holder force was 40 kN, and the punch velocity was 8 mm/s. It was also evident that the changes in the blank holder force had the most influence on the forming depth.
3. Changes in the carbon fibre orientations of different regions were observed in the square cup deep drawing. In the case of the bend-and-straighten region, there was no change in the carbon fibre orientation because only the simple bending of the material occurred. However, in the case of the deep draw region, there was an abrupt change in the carbon fibre orientation according to the drawing process.
4. Different changes in the thicknesses of the materials were observed for different regions. In the case of the CR340LA, the thickness decreased at the die and punch radii. On the other hand, in case of the CFRP, the greatest thickness reduction was found at the punch radius, while the thickness increased at the die radius.
5. A delamination defect was observed at the die radius region. It was observed that as the thinning rate increased, fewer voids were present.

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6 Declaration of conflicting interests

Author's name should include first name, middle initial (if desired) and surname, and be written centred, in 11pt Times New Roman, 11 pt below the title.

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7 Table

Table1. Properties of plain weave CFRP prepreg (CF3327EPC, HANKUK CARBON).

Construction	Carbon fibre weight (gr/m^2)	Resin weight (gr/m^2)	Resin content (%)	Total weight (gr/m^2)	Fabric thickness (mm)
Plain	205	150	42±2	352	0.27±0.050

Table2. Properties of carbon fibre (T300-3K-50, TORAY) and CR340LA.

Type	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Density (g/cc)	n
3K Carbon fibre	3530	230000	1.5	1.76	-
CR340LA	396	496	27	-	0.18

Table3. Die dimensions for the square cup deep drawing.

	Lower die (mm)	Punch (mm)	Blank (mm)	Tolerance between die and punch, δ_0 (mm)	Clearance, c
width (a)	50.3	45.7	90	2.3	0.888
length (b)	40.2	35.6	80	2.3	0.888

Table 4. The thickness of the blank and the number of layers.

	Sheet thickness (<i>mm</i>)	Sheets	Blank thickness (<i>mm</i>)
CFRP ($t_{0,c}$)	0.27	7	1.89
CR340LA ($t_{0,s}$)	0.7	1	0.7
Total (t_0)			2.59

